

SALES PROMOTIONS AS A CATALYST: ANALYZING THEIR INFLUENCE ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENT IN NIGERIAN BREWERIES, ENUGU, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study examined the influence of sales promotion strategies on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries product. Specifically, the study sought to: ascertained the influence of contest on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu, Nigeria, and determine the influence of price off on consumers' intention to purchase coca cola product in Enugu State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design was adopted in this study. The population of the study comprises of consumers of Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State. The data generated was analyzed using simple percentage and frequency tables. Linear multiple regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses. This was done with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. 0. The study showed that sales contest and Prize-off have a significant effect on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries product. Based on the findings of this study, the study recommended that among others that Nigerian Breweries should make sure that sales contest is free and fair contest in other to increase customers' intention to purchase.

Keywords: Sales promotion strategies, Contest, Price off and Consumers' intention.

1.1 Introduction

Purchase intention is a mediating variable between attitudes and behaviour and is a frequent predictor of consumer behaviour in research in the marketing field. It serves as a link between buying attitudes and buying behaviour in understanding consumers' buying behaviour, whether a consumer buys a product is more influenced by purchase intention than purchase attitude (Jun, Jang, & Han 2014). The consumer's purchase intention can be seen as the willingness to buy a product and is a decisive factor that directly influences purchase behaviour and can therefore be said to be the consumer's expected planned future behaviour (Kim & Lee, 2020). Purchase intention indicates the consumer's willingness to perform a specific act of purchasing a product in the future. It can be judged by whether an individual has the willingness to take action on a specific issue. In addition, the higher the product

price, the greater the possibility of actual purchase behaviour and is an important variable in measuring a company's performance (Tian & Lee, 2020).

Purchase intention is a measure of consumer willingness to buy by identifying consumer demand for a product. Purchasing intention is a field of behavioural intention, which is the personal will & belief realized by the result of future behaviour such as the attitude formed by an individual towards a specific company. There is a close positive correlation between purchase intention & actual purchase behaviour. Therefore, purchase intention can be used as a predictor of actual purchase behaviour. It can also be said that when consumers decide whether to purchase a product, the influence of their purchase intention is greater than their attitude towards the product itself (Wu & Lee, 2020). The study of Mbaga (2016) noted that sales promotions have a significant impact on consumer's purchase intention and can outlast any competition. Furthermore, previous research has shown that distinct market segment reacts to sales promotions (Oyekunle, Tijani & Balogun 2022). Esfahani and Jafarzadeh (2012) found out in their studies that there is a significant relationship between psychological variables and sales promotion.

Over the years, sales promotion has influenced consumer's purchase intention to organizational products and company retention their patronage. Fueled by the rise of interactive media and industry leaders and trade groups have considered it ideal to adopt the notion of consumers' intention in the measurement mix (Cummins, 2007). Sales promotion is an indirect form of marketing promotion, which tends to stimulate quick action or boost sales. It is those promotional strategies other than personal selling, advertising and publicity that stimulate consumer purchase and dealers effectiveness such as display show, exhibition, coupon, free sampling, premium, trade allowance, point of purchase display, contest, free trial, refund, rebate and other selling effort that are usually of short term activities. Ebue (2000) reported that sales promotion is that something extra that can arouse interest creating a buying desire, which sparks an immediate reaction from customer, middleman or company sales force. Sales promotional conceptual review tools are usually of short duration and the aim is to move sales of a particular product or brand above the existing level sales would increase if more customers are attracted to the shop.

Several researchers have sought to explain this relationship between sales promotion and consumer intention to purchase. The Nigerian Breweries product is currently facing unprecedented competition, declining brand loyalty and increased promotional sensitivity. This situation has resulted in loss of sales revenue to the firms, sometimes so severe that some have to close down. Bello (2021) claimed that sales promotions becoming so common that firms are obliged to follow or risk losing market share or close down. Bello (2021) posited that sales promotion is the most important promotional contrivance essential for the products leading to product loyalty and good public perception of the product & effective & efficient sales promotion attracts consumers and evokes positive reaction. This study was conducted in Nigeria hence if it is replicated in Ghana may give varying results due to the demographic differences between the two countries.

None of these prior studies maintained concise focus on the subject of discourse. The study also established a scope gap, which buttresses the fact that there is a limited study on sale promotional strategies and consumer purchase intention in Nigeria. More so, studies conducted by Okoye (2021) was only examined the effect of sales

promotion on the marketing of Coca-Cola drinks in Anambra State. Most of the other related studies were conducted in different states on Nigeria. This observed dearth of research on sale promotional strategies and consumer purchase intention of Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu state has been considered as another motivation to execute this study.

The main objective of this study is to assess the effect of sales promotion strategies on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products. Specifically the study seek to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of contest on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu, Nigeria
- ii. Determine the effect of price off on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu, Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Sales Promotion

Sales promotion is an initiative undertaken by organizations to create awareness and increase sales, usage or trial of a product or services (Aderemi, 2003). Sales promotion refers to the provision of incentives to customers or to the distribution channel to stimulate demand for a product. Adrika, (2007) described sales promotion as "anything extra that can raise curiosity, develop a buying desire, and trigger an immediate response from clients, Middlemen Company's sales team." He went on to say that sales promotion is a term used to describe specific types of sales acceleration, personal selling, or exposure. It's regarded as a one-of-a-kind marketing endeavor. It comprises of short-term incentives intended to encourage purchasing.

American Marketing Association, (2010) defined sales promotions is defined as a media and non-media marketing pressures deployed to various potential customers, like consumers, dealers, and distributors, for a specified period in order to stimulate trial, boost consumer demand, and improve the product viability. (Mullin, 2010), Organizations employ sales promotion to boost volume, induce trial, improve customer loyalty, gain customers, increase product utilization, stimulate awareness, increase brand awareness, and stimulate interest. It is an important component of an organizations overall marketing strategy along with advertising, public relations and personal selling. Sales promotion acts as a competitive weapon by providing an extra incentive for the target audience to purchase or support one brand over the other. It is particularly effective in spurring product trials and unplanned purchases (Aderemi, 2003). Ohazulike (2007) stated that sales promotion has tools that firm utilize to achieve their aim, goal and objective .These tools enable firms to be successful in the field of sales and also harness.

Terence (2007) described sales promotion as a mediated form of communication from an identifiable source designed to persuade the receiver to take some actions, now or in the future. The increased importance of sales promotion as strategic tools in consumer markets has generated strong interest among practitioners and academics in understanding the mechanisms, effectiveness, and efficiencies of different sales promotion approaches. Agbonifoh, Ogwo, Nnolim & Nkamnebe (2007) posited that sales promotion is a critical tool for competitive advantage in view of increasing competition in the global market which has prompted organizations to ensure

satisfaction of customer needs and wants more efficiently and effectively than competitors. Indeed, for any organization to survive in this competitive situation, it is important for it to develop and implement strong marketing communication strategies that will enable it meet and beat competition. It should also be able help organizations gain strategic advantage in the market because of its capacity for direct inducement and offer of an extra value or incentive to the sales force, distributors, or the ultimate consumers with the objective of creating an immediate sale (Schultz & Robinson, 2010).

Sales Contest

Sales contests are short-term motivational tools. Conceptually, sales contests and other short-term incentives, such as commissions and bonuses, differ from each other. In sales contests, payment to salespeople is based on relative performance rather than absolute performance (Kalra & Shi 2001). Due to the importance of sales contests (Gopalakrishna *et al.* 2016), previous studies provide insights into contest design decisions based on analytical models (Kalra & Shi 2001) and laboratory experiments (Chen, Ham & Lim 2011). Sales contests are short-term incentives that managers use to motivate salespeople to meet sales targets. However, insights regarding the effectiveness of different types of sales contests in a field setting are scarce.

The goal of most sales contests is not necessarily to create more sales or increase revenue, but rather it is simply a way of encouraging consumers' intention purchase company product and to help business grow in other ways as well. With sales contests, you can set specific objectives that are clear and measurable, which will allow you to measure how successful the contest was in achieving those goals. Sales contests are great for increasing the focus and motivation of your team. They are also a great way to increase your sales velocity, which is the number of new leads or customers you generate per day. Sales contests work because they help you set specific targets that can help you achieve those goals of consumers' intention purchase product.

Kotler (2014) opined that sales contest is short term incentives to encourage the purchase or sales of products or service" which means that sales promotion is a short term intensive to increase the passion to buy goods or services. In addressing this neglect, our study investigates the effects of two types of sales contests (traditional sales contest and Throw down).

In contrast, Throw-down represents a new type of sales contest. In Throw-down, the salespeople are first segmented based on their past performance, and then, the salespeople within a particular segment compete with one another. Thus, in contrast to a traditional sales contest, where only the

Price Off

Promotional pricing is a sales strategy in which brands temporarily reduce the price of a product or service to attract prospects and customers. By lowering the price for a short time, a brand artificially increases the value of a product or service by creating a sense of scarcity. Promotional pricing can help with customer acquisition by encouraging cost-conscious shoppers to buy. It can increase revenue, build customer loyalty, and improve short-term cash flow.

Price off is one of the factors that influence consumers intention in the selection and determination of a product (Suranto & Djunaidi, 2021). Price off is one of the determinants of product selection that will affect buying interest

(Son & Kijboonchoo, 2018). The basis of consumer consumer's intention is the consideration of price off. Price off is one of the benchmarks for consumers if they have difficulty in evaluating and choosing a product or service. Today's consumers are smarter, more critical and more price conscious, more demanding and also approached by many competitors by offering the same or even better. The effect of price off is very influential and has a relationship with consumer's intention of a product (Gunawan & Herdinata, 2021). This is also one of the important factors in purchasing decisions, especially for products to be purchased which can be associated with consumer's intention in a product. Soengeng and Wahyoedi (2021); (Prayogi & Santosa 2019) which shows that there is an effect of price off on consumer's intention of purchasing a product.

Kotler & Armstrong (2008) ascertained that price off is a reduction in the direct price off paid by consumers for purchases over a certain period of time. Meanwhile demanding Tjiptono (2015) price off is a discount given by the seller to the buyer as a form of appreciation for certain activities that has been carried out. The indicators used in this study to measure the discount price variable adopted from the Chao & Liao (2016) study consisted of 3 indicators as follows: Offering an attractive price, meaning that the discount price given by the company to consumers can save consumers' expenses themselves. Providing benefits for consumers mean that when consumers buy products sold by offering a price off, the consumer will get many benefits both in purchasing at affordable prices. Provide value to consumers, meaning consumers will feel the value and impression of the products offered and the value given by the company.

Fill (2012) price off is a valuation approach where goods or products are offered in a good discounted buying price and it seems to be a reduced cost to the consumers, mostly applied in hypermarkets and point of purchase displays. Price off is reduce the price for a given quantity or increase the quantity available at the same price, thereby enhancing value and create an economic incentive to purchase (Raghubir & Corfman, 2019).

Empirical Review

Diansyah (2022) examined the effect of price and promotion on buying interest moderated by consumer behaviour. The research method used in this research is quantitative with Partial Least Square (PLS-SEM) technique and assisted by SmartPLS 3.0 software. The researcher chose the census technique in the sampling technique, namely all members of the general population in Jabodetabek were used as samples in this study to examine the effect of price and the direct effect of the related variables. The results of this study indicate that price has an effect on buying interest, the effect of promotion on buying interest, the influence of consumer behaviour on buying interest, moderation of consumer behaviour can strengthen the effect of price on buying interest, moderation of consumer behaviour can strengthen the influence of promotion on buying interest. Olubusola, Usman & Mustapha (2022) examined the effect of sales promotion on customer patronage of household appliances in Lagos State. The purpose of the study was to examine the effectiveness of sales promotion (discount, premiums, and demonstration) on customer patronage of household appliances. The methodology used was based on a descriptive research design. Questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. The sample size was determined using simple random sampling technique. The sample size was One hundred and twenty-four (124) respondents, which was further analyzed using multiple-regression analysis. The

findings revealed that there is a positive significant effect of sales promotion in terms of discounts and demonstration used in marketing and sales of household appliances to drive customer patronage. The study however found that the use of premium as a customer sales promotion to influence customer patronage of household appliances was insignificant. Orji, Oyenuga and Ahungwa, (2020) determined the effects of sales promotion on the consumer buying behaviour of food seasoning among Nigerian households using Nestle Nigeria Plc Maggi NAIJA POT brand as a case study. The study employed cross sectional research design and the population consists of consumers of Nestle product (Maggi seasoning) in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. The sample size is 246 determined using Topman's formula. Primary data was used through administration of questionnaire and regression analysis was used to test the relationship between the study variables. The findings revealed that most of the consumers enjoy the rebates which influence their decision before, during and after the purchase; there is a positive effect of free trial and free gift on consumer buying behaviour of Maggi NAIJAPOT in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. Awoniyi, Olufayo, Oyekunle and Osanyintolu (2021) ascertained the goal was to see how effective consumer sales promotions (discounts, rebates, premiums, and demonstrations) are at increasing over-the-counter (OTC) drug usage. A descriptive study design with multistage sampling procedures was employed as the methodology. A total of 400 people were included in the sample, which was then examined using regression analysis. The findings demonstrated that consumer sales promotion, such as premiums, discounts, and rebates, utilized in the marketing and sales of pharmaceutical items, had a substantial effect on driving customer patronage as a consumer sales reaction. Consumers' sales responses to demonstrations as a consumer sales promotion, on the other hand, were shown to be inconsequential in the study. Ezenyilimba, Mbah & Eze (2019) examined the influence of sales promotion on customer patronage of alcoholic beverages was investigated by). The study's major goal was to investigate the impact of sales promotions on customer loyalty. The study was conducted using a survey research design. A total of 115 people took part in the study. The data was analyzed using Multiple Regression Analysis. The study revealed that sales promotions have a considerable impact on client consumption of alcoholic beverages. Pembu, Fudamu & Ibrahim (2017) examined the impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance with reference to Flour Mills Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria. The population of this study was carved out of the entire staff of the Flour Mills of Nigeria Maiduguri, Borno State branch cutting across the Top, Middle and lower level management. The study employed both the primary and secondary sources of data collection. Questionnaires were administered to twenty (20) staff using random sampling techniques. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics such as percentage analysis in order to analyze the data and regression analyses were used for testing hypotheses. The result signifies that sales promotional strategies have positive and significant effects on organizational performance. Ibok (2015) also examined the nexus between brand identity and customer loyalty in Nigeria with specific reference to four Nigeria telecommunication companies (MTN, Etisalat, Airtel, and Globacom). Sample size was made of Two hundred and forty respondents and data was analyzed with the aid of simple regression method. Results revealed that there was strong and positive relationship between customer loyalty and brand identity in the context of telecommunication industry in Nigeria. Ndubisi and Moitung (2015) evaluated the impact of sales promotional tools, namely coupon, price,

discount, free sample, bonus pack, and in-store display, on product trial and repurchase behaviour of consumers in Malaysia. The qualitative research design was used and the authors sourced data from secondary sources. The results of the study show that price discounts, free samples bonus packs, and in-store display are associated with product trials. Kumar and Swaminathan (2015) studied the impact of coupons on brand state and how that impact decays over the life of the coupon. The authors use an econometric model design effect in terms of equivalent price reduction, assess the coupon effect over time allow retailers to double or triple the coupon value and provide both self-coupon and cross-coupon elasticity at different levels of aggregation. Findings indicate that the effect of doubling the face value of coupon results in more than a proportionate increase in cross-coupon elasticities are much smaller in magnitude than the average self-coupon price elasticity. Laroche (2015) determined the effect of coupons on consumer's brand categorization and choice process using fast-food restaurants in China. The study used survey method to sample randomly selected fast food restaurants in Belgium. Questionnaire was used to elicit data. Findings suggest that there are both direct and cross advertising effects. In other words, the presence of a coupon for a local brand has an impact on consumer's attitudes and intentions towards that brand.

Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted in this study. Descriptive research design is deemed fit for this study since it allows the collection of data from a sizable population in a highly economical way.

The population of the study comprises of consumers of Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu state, Nigeria. Since the population is unknown, as such the sample size of the consumers purchase intention of Nigerian Breweries products was determined with the aid of Topman's non-parametric sample size determination formula, applied when the population frame is unknown. The researchers therefore, conducted a pilot survey by selecting 100 respondents and presenting to them questions hinging on sales promotional strategies on consumers purchase intention towards Nigerian Breweries. "q" and "p" values obtained from their responses were recorded as, 40 and 60 respectively. Stated below is the Topman's formula for sample size determination

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

where

n = Sample size

z = The value of Z-score associated with the selected degree of confidence limit (95%) i.e. = constant = 1.96

p = probability of positive response 40/100 = 0.4

q = probability of negative response 60/100 = 0.6

e = tolerable error or error margin = 5% = 0.05

Substituting therefore,

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.4 \times 0.6}{(0.05)^2}$$

(0,05)

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.4 \times 0.6}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.0025}{0.0025} \times 0.921984$$

$$n = 368.$$

That is $n = 368$ approximately

368 respondents were sampled for the study after careful selection processes was made across the study area. Malhotra and Birks (2000) stated that between 300 and 530 respondents are considered acceptable sample size that are adequate for quantitative consumer survey, where the population is not known.

This study makes use of primary and secondary data. The primary source of data will be collected on a first-hand basis. This study makes use of questionnaire to generate the primary data.

Method of Data Analyses

Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses. This was done with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0.

Model Specification

$$Y = f(X),$$

$$CPE = f(SP), \quad Y = \text{Customer's Intention to Purchase}$$

$$X = \text{Sales Promotion}$$

$$Y = \text{Dependent variable}$$

$$X = \text{Independent variable}$$

$$f = \text{function}$$

$$CPE = (\text{dependent variable})$$

$$SP = (\text{independent variable})$$

Where: Y is a function of X

$$Y = f(X_1 + X_2)$$

ie Sales Promotional Variables.

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \mu$$

$$\alpha_0 = \text{Constant (Intercept)}$$

$$\beta_1 - \beta_2 = \text{Coefficient of parameter } X_1 - X_2$$

$$SC = \text{Sales Contest}$$

$$PO = \text{Price Off}$$

Decision Rule

Accept null hypothesis if the P-value is not within the range of research stipulated significant level (0.01, 0.05, 0.10) used as standard and reject null hypothesis if the P-value is within the stipulated significant level.

Data Analyses

Out of three hundred and seventy questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, three hundred and fifty were completed and returned for analysis.

Data relevant to the Research Questions

The tables and analysis presented below covers the research questions of this research work.

Question 1: To what extent do sales contest influence consumers’ intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries, Enugu state, Nigeria?

Table 1: Respondents on the influence sales contest on consumers’ intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products, Enugu state, Nigeria

S/ N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean
1	Sales contests create more sales or increase revenue	101 28.9%	126 36.0%	59 8.3%	46 13.1%	18 5.1%	3.74
2	Sales contests encouraging consumers intention purchase company product	129 36.9%	130 37.1%	61 17.4%	32 9.1%	8 2.3%	4.00
3	Sales contests help organizations set specific targets that can help customers and company	134 38.3%	147 40.9%	41 11.7%	11 3.1%	17 4.9%	4.05
4	Sales contests is short term incentives to encourage the purchase or sales of products	120 34.3%	143 48.3%	32 9.1%	22 6.3%	33 9.4%	3.86
5	Sales contests offers various parties a motivational boost to make purchases	127 36.3%	149 42.6%	43 12.3%	20 5.7%	11 3.1%	4.10

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 presents the influence sales contest on consumers’ intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products. Regarding the issue bordering on better Sales contests create more sales or increase revenue, 101(28.39%) of the total sample strongly agreed, 126 (36.0%) agreed, 46(13.1%) disagreed, 18(5.1%) strongly disagreed and 59 (14.8%) were undecided with a mean of 3.74. On Sales contests encouraging consumers intention purchase company product, 129 (36.9%) respondents strongly agreed and 130 (37.4%) agreed. On the other hand, 32(9.1%) respondents disagreed, 8(2.3%) strongly agreed and 61 (17.4%) undecided with a mean of 4.00.

Table 1 questions on whether Sales contests help organizations set specific targets that can help customers and company, 134 (38.3%) respondents strongly agreed and 147(40.9%) agreed. Conversely, 11(3.1%) disagreed, 17(4.9%) strongly disagreed and 41 (11.7%) were undecided with a mean of 4.05. Question on whether Sales contests is short term incentives to encourage the purchase or sales of products, 120(34.3%) respondents strongly agreed and 143 (48.3) agreed. On the other hand, 22(6.3%) disagreed, 33 (9.4%) strongly disagreed and 32 (9.1%) were undecided with a mean of 3.86. The result on Table 1 indicates that 127(36.3%) respondents strongly agreed that Sales contests offers various parties a motivational boost to make purchases, 149 (42.6%) disagreed, 20 (7%) 11 strongly disagreed and 43 (12.3%) were undecided with a mean of 4.10. Using a cutoff point of 2.50 for the

rating scale, all the items had mean scores above the cutoff point. This implies that sales contest influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu.

Question 2: To what degree does prize off influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries, Enugu state, Nigeria?

Table 2: Respondents view on the influence of Prize off on consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries product in Enugu State

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean
1	Price off is one of the determinants of product selection that will affect buying interest	95 27.1%	161 46.0%	8 2.3%	24 6.9%	12 3.4%	4.01
2	Consumers intention purchase is the consideration of price off	111 37.7%	166 47.4%	34 9.7%	37 10.8%	2 0.6%	3.99
3	Price off is one of the benchmarks for consumers evaluating and choosing a product or service	113 32.3%	133 38.0%	41 17.7%	54 15.4%	9 2.6%	3.89
4	Price off is very influential with consumers intention of a product	85 24.3%	163 46.6%	71 20.3%	25 7.1%	6 1.7%	3.87
5	price off offer valuation approach where goods or products are offered in a good discounted	101 28.9%	176 50.3%	34 9.7%	37 10.8%	2 0.6%	3.99

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows that 95 respondents representing 27.1% of the total sample strongly agreed that price off is one of the determinants of product selection that will affect buying interest, 161 (46.0%) agreed, 24 (6%) disagreed, 12 (3%) strongly disagreed while 8 (2.3%) were undecided with a mean of 4.01. On whether consumers intention purchase is the consideration of price off, 111(37.7%) respondents strongly agreed, 166 (47.6%) agreed, 37(10.8%) disagreed, 2 (0.6%) strongly disagreed and 34 (9.7%) were undecided with a mean of 3.99

Table 2 reveals that 113 (32.3%) respondents strongly agreed that price off is one of the benchmarks for consumers evaluating and choosing a product or service, 133(38.0%) agreed, 54(15.4%) disagreed, 9(2.6%) strongly disagreed while 41(17.7%) were undecided with a mean of 3.89. Table.2, shows that 85(24.3%) respondents agreed that price off is very influential with consumers intention of a product, 163(46.6%) agreed, 25(7.1%) disagreed, 6(1.7%) strongly disagreed and 71(20.3%) were undecided with a mean of 3.87.

Finally the table reveal that 101(27.8%) respondents strongly agreed that price off offer valuation approach where goods or products are offered in a good discounted, 176 (50.3%) agreed, 37(10.8%) disagreed, 2 (0.6%) strongly disagreed and 34 (9.9%) were undecided with a mean of 3.87. Using a cutoff mean score 2.50 for the rating scale,

all the items had means scores above the cutoff point. This implies that prize off influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Ho: Sales contest has no significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.770a	.593	.589		1.641

Predictors: (Constant), Sales contest

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression 353.412	1	353.412	131.192	.000b
Residual	242.447	90	2.694		
Total	595.859	91			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumers' Intention to Purchase

Predictors: (Constant), Sales contest

Table 5: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
B		Std. Error	Beta		
Consumers' Intention to Purchase	(Constant)	3.092	1.254	11.454	.016
Sales Contest	.809	.071	.770	11.454	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sales contest

From table 3, R-column presents the square root of R-Squared and is the correlation between the observed and predicted values. The "R" column represents the value of R, the linear correlation coefficient. R can be considered to be one measure of the sales contest of the prediction of the dependent variable; in this case, consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria. A value of .770 in our case, indicates a good

level of prediction. The "R-Square", also called the coefficient of determination, represents the R2 value, which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable. From our value of .593, we can observe that our independent variable, sales contest, explained 59.3% of the variability of our dependent variable, consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria, and 40.7% (100% - 59.3%) of the variation is caused by factors other than the predictor included in this model. At first glance, R-squared seems like an easy to understand statistic that indicates how well a regression model fits a data set. However, it does not tell us the entire story. Therefore, to get the full picture, one must consider the adjusted R2 value.

Unstandardized coefficients indicate how much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant. The regression coefficient provides the expected change in the dependent variable (here: consumers' intention to purchase for a one-unit increase in the independent variable. Here, the unstandardized coefficient for sales contest is 0.809. This means for every unit of independent variable, that is, in effect of sales contest to a manageable size, there is 0.809 increase in increase in consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria.

In T and Sig. Columns, the t-value of 11.454 and p-value 0.000 used in testing the null hypothesis that the coefficient/parameter is 11.454. Since we used a 2 tailed test, then we did compare each p-value to the per-selected value of alpha. Coefficients having p-values less than alpha are statistically significant. Here, the alpha is 0.05 (5%). In this case, the tests tell us that sales contest $P(.000) < 0.05$ is statistically significant. Thus, null hypothesis is rejected and we therefore conclude that sales contest has a significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Prize-off has no significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State. Nigeria

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.534a	.285	.277	2.176

a. Predictors: (Constant), Price-off

Table 7: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	169.645	1	169.645	35.822	.000b
Residual	426.214	90	4.736		
Total	595.859	91			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumers' intention to purchase

b. Predictors: (Constant), Prize-off

c.

Table 8: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
B		Std. Error	Beta		
Consumers' intention to purchase		8.712	1.455	5.985	.000
Prize-off	.498	.083	.534	5.985	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumers' intention to purchase

b. Prize-off

From the above table, R-column presents the square root of R-Squared and is the correlation between the observed and predicted values. The "R" column represents the value of *R*, the *linear* correlation coefficient. *R* can be considered to be one measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable; in this case, consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria. A value of .534 in our case, indicates a positive prediction.

The "R-Square", also called the coefficient of determination, represents the *R*² value, which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable. From our value of .285, we can observe that our independent variable, Prize-off, explained 28.5% of the variability of our dependent variable, consumers' intention to purchase of Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria, and 71.5% (100% - 28.5%) of the variation is caused by factors other than the predictor included in this model. At first glance, R-squared seems like an easy to understand statistic that indicates how well a regression model fits a data set. However, it does not tell us the entire story. Therefore, to get the full picture, one must consider the adjusted R² value.

As predictors are added to the model, each predictor will explain some of the variance in the dependent variable simply due to chance. One could continue to add predictors to the model which would continue to improve the ability of the predictors to explain the dependent variable, although some of this increase in R-square would be simply due to chance variation in that particular sample. The adjusted R-square attempts to yield a more honest value to estimate the R-squared for the population.

However, in the case, it is only one independent variable against the dependent variable because it is a linear regression model. In our case therefore, the adjusted R-square value is .277 which is 27.7%, which is about 0.8% (28.5 - 27.7 = 0.8) different from the main R-squared.

Unstandardized coefficients indicate how much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant. The regression coefficient provides the expected change in the

dependent variable (here: consumers' intention to purchase y) for a one-unit increase in the independent variable (here: Prize-off). Here, the unstandardized coefficient for Prize-off is 0.498. This means that for every unit increase of independent variable, Prize-off, there is 0.498 increase in consumers' intention to purchase.

Prize-off has a significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries products in Enugu State, Nigeria

In T and Sig. Columns, the t-value was 5.985 and p-value was 0.000. Since we used a 2 tailed test, then we did compare each p-value to the preselected value of alpha. Coefficients having p-values less than alpha are statistically significant. Here, the alpha is 0.05 (5%). In this case therefore, the tests tell us that technology $p(.000) < 0.05$ is statistically significant. Thus, null hypothesis is rejected and we therefore conclude that Prize-off has a significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries product in Enugu, Nigeria

Conclusion and Recommendations

This work evaluated the effect of sales promotional strategies on consumers purchase intention towards Nigerian Breweries products, using contest and price off as the independent variables on consumers' purchase intention. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The study showed that sales contest and Prize-off have a significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries product. Therefore, the study concluded that Sales promotional strategies had a positive significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase Nigerian Breweries product in Enugu, Nigeria.

Based on the findings and the conclusion of this study, the study recommended that:

1. Nigerian Breweries should make sure that sales contest is free and fair contest in other to increase customers' intention to purchase
2. The company management should dedicate to exploring consumer demands, constantly innovate, provide competitive products conforming to consumer demands, offer consumers with favorable price-off promotion in other to reinforce consumer trust in the brand.

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